

Characterization of LaGPS:Ce scintillation crystals obtained under reducing atmosphere

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Abstract

Ce-doped lanthanum gadolinium pyrosilicate are among the most efficient oxide scintillation crystal with a light yield of ca. 40000 ph./MeV and a high energy resolution. Meanwhile, the process of obtaining these crystals, as well as other rare-earth silicates, involves the use of iridium equipment in a weakly oxidizing gas atmosphere. The work is devoted to the optimization of obtaining process by the Czochralski method from tungsten crucibles in a reducing atmosphere and characterization of (La,Gd)₂Si₂O₇:Ce (LaGPS:Ce) crystals. Transparent ingots with the length of up to 40 mm were obtained. Post-growth high-temperature annealing in an oxidizing atmosphere significantly improves the scintillation characteristics of LaGPS:Ce, which are not inferior to those in crystals obtained by a conventional technology from iridium crucibles.

1. Introduction

Single crystals of Ce-doped lanthanum gadolinium pyrosilicate (Gd_{1-x-y}La_xCe_y)₂Si₂O₇ (LaGPS:Ce) of various structural modifications are one of the most efficient oxide scintillators. This material combines a high light output, good energy resolution, short decay time of luminescence, relatively high density, radiation tolerance [1-5]. A peculiar features of this material are outstanding temperature stability of the light output at elevated temperatures, and registration of thermal neutrons due to the presence of ¹⁵⁷Gd having the highest thermal-neutron capture cross-

section among any stable nuclei [6-8]. The disadvantage of this material is its poor manufacturability, namely, crystals are grown from iridium crucibles in a weakly oxidizing atmosphere at temperatures of approximately 1800 °C. Such conditions imply a rapid oxidation, deformation and destruction of iridium crucibles [9]. As the processing of iridium crucibles is a major component of the crystal cost and bearing in mind the record high Ir prices on the market [10], there is no reliable method of mass production for bulk rare-earth pyrosilicates.

The problem of Ir crucibles substitution with Mo or W crucibles is successfully solved for rare earth aluminates, such as rare earth garnets and perovskites by applying reducing atmosphere conditions in Czochralski or Bridgman processes. A transfer of these technologies to rare earth silicate growth is complicated due to interaction between SiO₂ and CO gas formed in the growth atmosphere due to interaction graphite heat insulation with residual oxygen [11]. In the previous study of our group [11] we demonstrated the possibility of obtaining Ce-doped crystals of yttrium oxyorthosilicate and lanthanum gadolinium pyrosilicate from W/Mo crucibles by controlling atmosphere composition and modifying the crystallizer. However, numerous inclusions in the form of gas bubbles deteriorated crystal transparency. As a sequence, a light yield of LaGPS:Ce obtained by the Czochralski method from Mo crucible in reducing gas atmosphere was ca. 22000 ph./MeV with an energy resolution of 17 %, remarkably worse compared to the best examples of LaGPS:Ce grown from Ir crucibles in weakly oxidizing gas atmosphere [1-3]. Temperature annealing in oxidizing conditions is a conventional method of eliminating oxygen vacancies in oxide crystals grown under oxygen-poor conditions. In [12], we showed the effect of high-temperature annealing on the scintillation parameters of rare-earth garnets obtained in a reducing atmosphere from W crucibles. Such annealing also has a positive effect on the scintillation characteristics of rare earth silicate crystals [13-15] obtained in a weakly oxidizing atmosphere from iridium crucibles, in particular, crystals based on gadolinium and lutetium pyrosilicates [16, 17]. This work is aimed to enhance the preparation process of LaGPS:Ce improve the scintillation performance of LaGPS:Ce obtained in a reducing atmosphere from a W crucible. We performed a detailed characterization of the obtained crystals annealed in oxidizing conditions at different temperatures.

2. Experiment

2.1. Crystal growth, sample preparation and thermal treatment

Crystals were obtained by the Czochralski method in an Ar + CO atmosphere from a tungsten crucible of 50 mm in diameter and 30 mm height with carbon insulation in a radiofrequency heating furnace "Oxide". The initial oxides (Gd₂O₃, La₂O₃, CeO₂, SiO₂) with a purity of not worse than 99.99 % were mixed in the composition of (Ce_{0.01}La_{0.39}Gd_{0.6})₂Si₂O₇. The mixture was loaded

into the crucible in several "heating-cooling" stages while the melt level was 5 mm below the upper edge of the crucible. All "heating-cooling" stages were carried out in a crucible heated with a tungsten lid. During the crystal growth process, a tungsten screen was placed over the crucible. A tungsten rod of 2 mm in diameter was used as a seed. The crystal pulling rate was 1 mm/h and the rotation rate varied within 6-12 rpm at different growth stages. The crystal diameter was automatically controlled by weighing the crystal.

Samples of $5 \times 5 \times 1.5 \text{ mm}^3$ were cut from the inclusion-free part of a crystal, and both $5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ sides polished for optical and scintillation studies.

The samples were annealed in air at a temperature of 1200 °C for 12 hours (sample 1), 1300 °C for 6 hours (sample 2) and 1200 °C for 6 hours (sample 3).

2.2. XRD measurements

X-ray study was carried out using «Xcalibur-3» automated diffractometer (Oxford Diffraction Ltd.) (MoK α -radiation, graphite monochromator, «Sapphire-3» CCD detector). The powder diffraction study was carried out using a «Siemens D500» diffractometer (CuK α radiation, Bragg-Brentano geometry, graphite monochromator on the diffracted beam, $5^\circ < 2\theta < 90^\circ$, $\Delta(2\theta) = 0.02^\circ$). The structure was solved with SHELX program package [18-20] and refined using full-matrix least squares in the anisotropic approximation. The WinGX, PLATON and VESTA programs [19] were used for the analysis of the structure and preparation of illustrations. Data were processed in the program package FullProf-2008 program [21].

2.3. Optical measurements

Absorption spectra of LaGPS:Ce crystals in the 200-400 nm spectral range were measured using a UV/visible optical absorption spectrometer Specord200 (Analytik Jena, USA). Photoluminescence (excited at 270 nm) and photoluminescence excitation spectra were recorded with a spectrofluorimeter Lumina (Thermo Scientific, USA).

Luminescence decay curves were collected using a picosecond spectrofluorimeter FluoTime 200 (PicoQuant, Germany) operated in Time-Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC) mode. As an excitation source, a pulsed LED PLS 270 with the emission wavelength of 270 nm (PicoQuant, Germany) was used. The Instrumental Response Function (IRF) was about 650 ps. The obtained fluorescence decay curves were analyzed using FluoFit software for data analysis (PicoQuant, Germany). Decay kinetic profiles under 320 nm were measured at 300 K using a combined fluorescent lifetime and steady-state spectrometer FLS 920 (Edinburgh Instruments)

equipped with hydrogen filled nF 900 nanosecond flashlamp (optical pulse duration is 1.0–1.6 ns, pulse repetition rate is 40 kHz) for time correlated single photon counting measurements.

2.4. Scintillation measurements

Scintillation decay time spectra were measured with Hamamatsu R6231 PMT excited with 662 keV gamma ray from ^{137}Cs source. Signal from PMT anode was transferred to the input of Rigol DS6064 19 oscilloscope. The light yield was determined by comparing the peak position at pulse height spectra of our crystals and of BGO crystal (8600 ph./MeV with an energy resolution of 11.9%). The measurements were recorded using a pulse processing chain consisting of an R1307 PMT (Hamamatsu, Japan), a charge-sensitive preamplifier BUS 2-95 24 (Tensor, Russia), a custom shaping amplifier and a multichannel analyser AMA-03F (Tensor, 25 Russia). ^{137}Cs (662 keV) was used as a gamma-ray source.

All measurements were made at room temperature (25 °C).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Crystal growth and crystal structure

The grown LaGPS:Ce ingot is shown in Figure 1a. The crystal diameter was 15 mm and the length of the boule was 90 mm. The upper part of the ingot was polycrystalline, while lower part was single crystalline, transparent, and mainly free from visible gas inclusions and surface etching, which were observed in the previous study [11]. This was attributed to the reduced impact of the CO-containing growth atmosphere. This became possible due to the minimization of CO circulation over the melt and near the crystal surface by introducing a lid above the crucible during loading the crucible with charge as well as due to the screen located above the crucible during crystal growth.

Polycrystallinity of upper part of the ingot can be associated with both seeding onto a metal rod, and incongruent melting of GPS compound [22], as even in the case of heavy REE-doping the compound remains pseudo-congruent and grows essentially from the melt-solution [23]. XRD analysis of the upper part showed just the pyrosilicate phase without foreign phases (Figure 1b). The polycrystalline and single crystalline parts possess the same crystalline structure. The main crystallographic data are summarized in Table 1.

a

b

Figure 1. Photo of as-grown LaGPS:Ce crystal (a), LaGPS:Ce XRD spectra (b).

Table 1. LaGPS:Ce main crystallographic data.

Empirical formula	$\text{Gd}_{1.33}\text{La}_{0.67}\text{O}_7\text{Si}_2$
Formula weight M_r , a.m.u	470.39
T , K	293(2)
λ (MoK α), Å	0.71073
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, $P2_1/n$
Unit cell dimensions (Å, °)	$a=5.39850(10)$, $b=8.6198(2)$, $c=12.9535(2)$, $\beta=90.400(2)$
Cell volume V , Å ³	602.76(2)
Z	4
Calculated density d_x , g/cm ³	5.183
Final R indices (observed refl. ($I > 2\sigma(I)$))	$R_1=0.0633$, $wR^2=0.1898$

According to the XRD analysis data, the obtained crystal possesses monoclinic structure with the spatial symmetry group $P2_1/n$. In accordance with [24], this type of symmetry coincides with the structural type G and corresponds to rare-earth pyrosilicates of lanthanum, cerium, praseodymium, niobium, and samarium. The average radius of the rare-earth cation in the obtained crystal is 0.96 Å (calculated by the formula from [25]), which is very close to the ionic radius of Sm^{3+} (0.95 Å) [26]. The atomic numbering scheme, thermal ellipsoids and the crystal packing are shown in Figure 2 (a, b).

Figure 2. Numbering scheme and thermal ellipsoids (50 % probability level) for LaGPS (a), polyhedral representation for LaGPS. Gd, La, Si, O atoms are shown in pink, green, blue, red color, respectively (b).

Obtained results show that RE atoms in the structure occupy two eight-coordinated positions, but Gd^{3+} substitutes with La^{3+} only in the Gd(2) positions (Figure 2). Herein, the volumes of Gd(1) and Gd(2) polyhedra are appreciably slightly differ (24.55 \AA^3 and 27.93 \AA^3 for Gd(1) and Gd(2) resp.) (accordingly to official IUCr structure-validation suite (check CIF/PLATON) [27]) i.e. larger La^{3+} ions atoms reasonably substitute Gd^{3+} in larger polyhedra.

3.2. Optical properties

Optical absorption spectrum of LaGPS:Ce shown in Figure 3a is typical for GPS-based crystals and completely coincides in shape with that of LaGPS:Ce possessing a triclinic structure described in [28]. The band gap of LaGPS:Ce according to [29] is about 6.6-6.8 eV, and bands of $4f-5d_x$ ($x = 1,2,3,4,5$) transitions should be represented in the UV-VUV absorption spectrum. In our case, there are no structured Ce^{3+} peaks due to a relatively large Ce^{3+} concentration and a very high optical density of Ce^{3+} in this range, just wide bands in the 270-350 nm and <250 nm both at

absorption and excitation spectra. The same spectral shape was observed in many earlier studies, see, for example [11, 31]. The photoluminescence spectrum (Figure 3b) contains a typical luminescence bands peaked at 367 nm and 390 nm associated with the transition to $^2F_{5/2}$ and $^2F_{7/2}$ terms of the split ground state of Ce^{3+} ions [29] excited in the UV-band. Furthermore, the peaks at 273 and 276 nm corresponding to the $^6P_{7/2} \rightarrow ^8S_{7/2}$ radiative transition of Gd^{3+} [30] are clearly distinguishable at the absorption spectra.

a

b

Figure 3. Optical absorption spectrum of LaGPS: Ce (a), luminescence excitation (left) and emission (right) spectra (b).

a

b

Figure 4. Luminescence decay curves of LaGPS:Ce under 270 nm excitation (a) and 320 nm excitation (b).

The photoluminescence decay curves under Ce^{3+} intracenter excitation (270 nm) (Figure 4a) are approximated by two exponentials with time constants 34 ns and 450 ns, while the excitation at 320 nm yields single fast component (Figure 4b). The presence of the slow component in the

first case may be related to the overlap of Ce^{3+} and Gd^{3+} excitation bands at 270 nm with subsequent delayed energy transfer via Gd^{3+} sublattice. One should not rule out the thermal ionization of Ce^{3+} ions and the electron transitions from the Ce^{3+} excited 5d levels of cerium to the conduction band; subsequently, these electrons can again take part in radiative recombination on cerium ions, giving delayed luminescence, as observed in [29]. Nevertheless, verification of these assumptions requires more detailed research.

3.3. Scintillation properties

The amplitude spectra of three LaGPS:Ce samples and the reference BGO sample are shown in Figure 5a.

a

b

c

Figure 5. LaGPS:Ce amplitude spectra (a), absorption spectra (b), luminescence kinetics (c) upon excitation by 662 keV gamma quanta of a ^{137}Cs source.

The highest value of relative light output of LaGPS:Ce was approximately 400 % of that in BGO (sample 3). The variations in the light output magnitude for the three samples are probably associated with different transparency of them (Figure 5b). One may see that the light output clearly correlated with absorption: it increases with a decrease in the absorption. As the shape of the absorption spectra is similar, the changes in absorption were attributed to the different concentrations of scattering centres in the samples.

The absolute light yield of sample 3 reached 24100 ph./MeV with an energy resolution of 10 % (Table 2). This value remarkably lower than the best values of the light yield described in the literature [32] but coincided with that presented in our previous work [11]. On the other hand, energy resolution almost doubled in comparison to [11], which indicates the improved quality of the crystals obtained in this work. The luminescence decay under gamma excitation with an energy of 662 keV of a ^{137}Cs source is approximated by two exponentials (Figure 5c) with time constants of 77 ns and 670 ns. Slower decay at extrinsic excitation (for example, under X- or γ -rays) as compared to the PL decay at intrinsic excitation is a typical situation, because in the first case some time is needed for carriers to reach a luminescence center, while a luminescence center is directly excited at intrinsic excitation.

3.4. Effect of annealing

The light yield of crystal samples annealed in an oxidizing atmosphere increased significantly with the highest value of 38400 ph./MeV observed after annealing at 1200 °C for 12 hours (Figure 6a, sample 1), and the energy resolution was improved up to 7.1 %. However, the largest increase in the light output value is observed for sample 2, which was annealed at a higher temperature of 1300 °C for 6 hours. Decay times after annealing decreased a bit down to 70 ns (79 %), but remained rather long and with the contribution of the slower component at 640 ns (21 %) (Figure 6b, Table 2). Similar values of the decay times for a crystal of identical composition grown from Ir crucibles in a weakly oxidizing atmosphere were obtained in [3]. The light yield enhancement and shortening of the decay time after annealing may be attributed to the minimization of oxygen vacancy concentration and partial transfer of Ce^{3+} into the tetravalent states. The positive impact of coexisting Ce^{3+} and Ce^{4+} centers was reported for different Ce-doped scintillators [33, 34] .

a

b

Figure 6. Amplitude spectra (a), luminescence decay (b) gamma-excitation after the heat treatment at 1300 °C for 6 hours.

Table 2. Scintillation properties of LaGPS:Ce under γ -excitation 662 keV ^{137}Cs in comparison with the counterparts grown by Czochralski method in Ir crucibles [2, 6, 35].

Sample	LY, ph./MeV/R, %		τ , ns/contribution, %			
	before annealing	after annealing	before annealing		after annealing	
LaGPS:Ce [2, 6]	ND*	38000	ND	ND	25-35	ND
LaGPS [33]	ND	38000-43000	ND	ND	60-70	ND
LaGPS:Ce 1	23100/10.1	38400/7.1 (1200C 12h)	80/76%	682/24%	70/79%	640/21%
LaGPS:Ce 2	20100/12.4	37800/7.9 (1300C 6h)	75/75%	662/25%	74/78,5%	650/21,5%
LaGPS:Ce 3	24100/10	33300/22.3 (1200C 6h)	77/75%	670/25%	72/77%	639/23%

*ND: no data available

Conclusions

Preparation process of LaGPS:Ce in a reducing Ar-CO atmosphere from a W crucible was optimized to reduce the number of scattering centres in crystals. The light yield after high-temperature oxidative annealing reaches 38400 ph./MeV, and the energy resolution of 7.1 % at 662 keV, which similar to the values described in the literature for crystals grown under weakly oxidizing conditions from Ir crucibles. A proposed process is cost-efficient compared to the

conventional technology employing Ir crucibles and may be promising for mass production of rare-earth pyrosilicate crystals for scintillators and other applications.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the project «Carbon-2» of National Academy of Science of Ukraine, International Research Project “ScintLab” of CNRS, France, and French-Ukrainian bilateral project “Dnipro”(agreement with Ministry of Science and Education of Ukraine M/44-2022 by 24.05.2022). Oleg Sidletskiy acknowledges the support from “ENSEMBLE3” project (GA no. MAB/2020/14) carried out within the International Research Agendas program of the Foundation for Polish Science and Teaming for Excellence project (GA no. 857543)". Authors are grateful to Dr. Jakub Cajzl and Dr. Johann Toudert (Ensemble3 Centre of Excellence, Warsaw, Poland) for providing the measurements of optical transmission.

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